

Doctor–patient communication in outpatient neurology: a narrative review from semiotic and pragmatic perspectives

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ABSTRACT

Background and objectives. The doctor–patient relationship is particularly important in neurology, where cognitive impairment, language disorders, emotional vulnerability, and chronic disease trajectories may complicate clinical dialogue. Communication lies at the center of this collaborative relationship and may influence patient understanding, adherence, satisfaction, and engagement in care. This narrative review provides an integrated perspective on neurologist–patient communication by combining semiotic, pragmatic, and clinical approaches, with attention to verbal, nonverbal, and paraverbal communication during outpatient consultations.

Materials and methods. This article is a narrative review and conceptual analysis. Sources were identified from databases and academic platforms including Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed, Google Scholar, and ScienceDirect, using keywords related to clinical communication, doctor–patient relationship, neurological consultation, empathy, semiotics, pragmatics, verbal communication, nonverbal communication, and paraverbal communication. Peer-reviewed articles, books, reviews, and theoretical studies relevant to medical communication and neurological practice were considered.

Conclusions. Medical communication may be understood as both a science and an art. In outpatient neurology, effective dialogue requires attention to three complementary perspectives: (1) the diachronic perspective, which recalls the historical development of communication and rhetoric; (2) the semiotic perspective, which interprets communication as a system of signs and codes; and (3) the pragmatic perspective, which emphasizes the appropriate use of language and behavior in specific clinical contexts. Awareness of these dimensions may help neurologists adapt communication to patients’ cognitive, emotional, and sociocultural characteristics and support clearer, more respectful, and more patient-centered care. From a lifestyle medicine perspective, effective communication is also essential for patient engagement, adherence to long-term recommendations, and sustainable behavioral change.

Keywords: medical communication, doctor–patient relationship, neurological consultation, semiotics, pragmatics, outpatient neurology

INTRODUCTION

Establishing high-quality, collaborative relationships with patients is one of the main objectives of neurological practice. This goal is not always easy to achieve, because neurologists may encounter major communication barriers related to cognitive impairment, neurocognitive disorders, aphasia, emotional distress, or reduced capacity to express health concerns. Under these circumstances, the physician ben-

efits from a deeper understanding of the communication process and from the ability to adapt dialogue to the specific needs of the neurological patient.

Neurologist–patient communication can be understood through several complementary perspectives. A semiotic perspective highlights the role of signs, codes, and meanings in the interpretation of symptoms and clinical information. A pragmatic perspective emphasizes how language is used in context,

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how messages are adapted to the interlocutor, and how communication influences behavior and decision-making. A diachronic perspective reminds us that the art of persuasion, rhetoric, and interpersonal communication has been explored since antiquity and continues to inform contemporary professional dialogue.

This narrative review examines doctor–patient communication in outpatient neurology through semiotic, pragmatic, and historical perspectives, with particular attention to verbal, nonverbal, and paraverbal communication. Within the framework of Lifestyle Medicine, effective communication extends beyond diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic recommendations. It represents a key determinant of patient engagement, shared decision-making, long-term adherence to lifestyle interventions, and self-management of chronic neurological disorders. Strengthening communication skills may therefore contribute not only to better clinical encounters but also to sustainable behavioral changes that support neurological health and overall well-being.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This article is a narrative review based on an interdisciplinary analysis of the literature addressing doctor–patient communication, with particular emphasis on outpatient neurological practice. Unlike a systematic review, the objective was to provide a conceptual synthesis integrating perspectives from medicine, communication sciences, semiotics, pragmatics, psychology, and the history of medical communication.

The literature search included publications indexed in PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Science Direct, and Google Scholar. The search strategy combined keywords such as *doctor–patient communication*, *neurology*, *outpatient consultation*, *medical communication*, *clinical communication*, *semiotics*, *pragmatics*, *empathy*, *shared decision-making*, *nonverbal communication*, *paraverbal communication*, and *patient-centered care*.

Peer-reviewed articles, review papers, clinical guidelines, book chapters, and seminal theoretical works published primarily in English were considered. Historical references were included when they provided conceptual foundations relevant to the evolution of communication theory or contemporary medical practice. Preference was given to publications directly applicable to neurological consultations and communication in chronic disease management.

The selected literature was analyzed thematically. Evidence was synthesized into four principal domains: (1) the historical evolution of medical communication; (2) semiotic and pragmatic perspectives relevant to clinical encounters; (3) verbal, nonver-

bal, and paraverbal communication in neurological practice; and (4) practical implications for outpatient neurological consultations and patient-centered care within the framework of Lifestyle Medicine.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

About communication

The field of medical humanities has expanded substantially and offers valuable insights for medical education, including the development of communication skills [1]. In this context, the communication process should be understood from both linguistic and medical perspectives.

Communication is a continuous and complex process, widely interpreted in specialized literature. Individuals may act both as senders and receivers, while the purpose of communication is to be understood, accepted, and respected by the interlocutor. Communication is a social phenomenon that develops within human interaction. Human language and communicative abilities are closely related to the need to cooperate and coordinate actions with others [2]. Therefore, people communicate in order to share thoughts, emotions, and experiences, regardless of their social or professional role.

The way individuals communicate influences both private and public life. Professional development depends not only on technical knowledge but also on communication skills. To build effective dialogue, it is important to understand social and communicative intentions, because the human brain is able to attribute goals and intentions to actions and to interpret not only what a person does, but also why they do it [3]. Social intentions influence the course of communication and should therefore be correctly recognized and interpreted in dialogue.

Communication from a diachronic perspective

The role of communication in interpersonal relationships has attracted scholarly interest since antiquity [4,5]. Among the earliest attempts to conceptualize communication are those of the ancient Greek philosophers and rhetoricians. Gorgias argued that truth is difficult to know and even more difficult to communicate [6]. Corax of Syracuse, regarded as one of the founders of rhetoric, developed *The Art of Rhetoric*, whose principles were later expanded by his disciple Tisias. Plato considered rhetoric distinct from science because it operates within the realm of probability and opinion rather than certainty [7]. Aristotle subsequently refined rhetorical theory, placing it within the domain of practical reasoning and defining its philosophical foundations. Quintilian further emphasized the ethical dimension of communication, arguing that effective rhetoric is inseparable from moral character [7].

From the Greco-Roman period until the Enlightenment, communication continued to be discussed primarily from a practical perspective. Interest in communication theory expanded considerably from the seventeenth century onward, leading to multiple theoretical approaches. John Fiske classified these into two major traditions: the process (or pragmatic) school, which views communication primarily as the transmission of messages, and the semiotic school, which understands communication as the production and exchange of meaning [14]. During the twentieth century, communication became an independent interdisciplinary field, driven largely by advances in communication technologies, industrialization, globalization, and the increasing complexity of human interactions [8].

Today, communication is recognized as a multi-dimensional process relevant to virtually every area of society, including healthcare. Understanding its historical evolution provides a broader conceptual framework for contemporary medical communication and helps clinicians appreciate the theoretical foundations underlying effective doctor–patient relationships. Although historical perspectives remain valuable, they should complement – not replace – current evidence on patient-centered communication and clinical practice.

Communication from a semiotic perspective

People live in communities because they share meanings, values, and experiences, and communication is the mechanism through which these common understandings are created and maintained. It is an interactive social process involving multiple participants and constitutes the foundation of interpersonal relationships [9]. Developing effective communication skills requires an understanding of both the semiotic and pragmatic dimensions of communication [10,11].

From a semiotic perspective, communication is the process of transmitting and interpreting messages through systems of signs and codes [12,13]. John Fiske argued that all communication involves signs and codes: signs are objects or actions that represent something beyond themselves, whereas codes are organized systems that govern how signs relate to one another and how they are interpreted [14]. In other words, signs convey meaning, while codes provide the framework through which that meaning is understood.

In the clinical setting, this perspective has practical implications. Patients communicate through verbal descriptions, facial expressions, gestures, tone of voice, and behavior, while physicians interpret these signs together with clinical findings to formulate diagnostic hypotheses and management plans. It is important to distinguish this semiotic perspective from

clinical semiology, which focuses specifically on the recognition and interpretation of signs and symptoms of disease.

Two principal dimensions of meaning are generally recognized within communication. Denotative meaning refers to the direct and objective meaning of words, whereas connotative meaning encompasses emotional, cultural, and contextual associations. In doctor–patient communication, particularly in neurology, clear and precise language is often desirable when explaining diagnoses, investigations, or therapeutic recommendations. Nevertheless, effective communication also requires empathy and sensitivity, and emotionally supportive language should complement rather than replace precise medical terminology.

Consequently, successful neurologist–patient communication depends not only on selecting accurate words but also on choosing verbal and non-verbal signs that are appropriate to the patient's cognitive status, emotional condition, health literacy, and sociocultural background. Awareness of these semiotic principles may contribute to more effective, patient-centered communication during outpatient neurological consultations.

Communication from a pragmatic perspective

Pragmatics examines how language is used in specific contexts and how meaning is shaped by the relationship between speakers, their intentions, and the circumstances in which communication occurs [15]. In clinical practice, the same message may produce different effects depending on how, when, and to whom it is delivered.

The pragmatic dimension of communication was extensively developed by researchers associated with the Palo Alto School, including Paul Watzlawick, Gregory Bateson, and Don Jackson. They emphasized that communication extends beyond the simple exchange of information and constitutes a dynamic process through which individuals create and negotiate social reality. Every communicative act therefore contains both informational and relational components.

In medical practice, attention should be directed not only to the content of the message but also to its context. The physician must consider the patient's emotional state, cognitive abilities, cultural background, previous medical experiences, and expectations before delivering clinical information. Appropriate communication requires adapting language, tone, and the amount of information to the patient's needs and capacity for understanding.

In outpatient neurology, pragmatic competence is particularly important because many patients experience cognitive impairment, language disorders, anxiety, or uncertainty regarding their diagnosis and

prognosis. Under these circumstances, effective communication requires empathy, active listening, and flexibility. Physicians should encourage questions, verify patient understanding, and adapt explanations whenever necessary. These strategies facilitate shared decision-making and strengthen the therapeutic alliance.

From the perspective of Lifestyle Medicine, the pragmatic component of communication extends beyond the clinical encounter itself. Lifestyle interventions frequently require long-term behavioral changes, and their success depends largely on the patient's understanding, motivation, and sustained engagement. Consequently, communication should be viewed not only as a means of transmitting medical information but also as a tool for supporting self-management, adherence to recommendations, and healthier lifestyle behaviors.

Medical communication: a specialized form of communication in the neurological context

Medical communication is a complex and multi-dimensional process through which healthcare professionals and patients exchange information about health, disease, diagnosis, treatment, and prevention. Its role is not limited to the transfer of medical information. A well-conducted dialogue can build trust, support shared decision-making, improve adherence to treatment, and increase patient satisfaction.

Several authors have emphasized the importance of communication skills in clinical practice. Romanian researchers define medical communication as the exchange of health-related information between healthcare professionals and patients [16]. Mahler observed that physicians are no longer the only source of medical knowledge, as patients increasingly obtain information from digital media and other public sources [17]. This reality requires clinicians to communicate clearly and accurately, while helping patients distinguish reliable medical information from misinformation [18].

Brindley and colleagues described communication as one of the clinician's greatest strengths or, when poorly performed, one of the greatest vulnerabilities [19]. Biglu et al. also emphasized that friendly and respectful communication is an essential component of medical practice and should be regarded as a core clinical competency, not as an optional interpersonal skill [20]. Gordon and colleagues further noted that good communication helps physicians establish and maintain therapeutic relationships even in difficult clinical situations [21].

Patient-centered communication may increase patient confidence, motivation, and satisfaction, while also strengthening the therapeutic relationship [22]. According to Howick et al., empathic and positive communication may improve several aspects of

clinical care, including patient experience, treatment adherence, and selected clinical outcomes [23]. Wu and colleagues highlighted communication as an important factor in reducing information asymmetry between physicians and patients and in supporting collaborative decisions about treatment [24]. Similar conclusions have been reported in other studies examining clinician–patient communication [25–29].

For the doctor–patient dialogue to be constructive, Ong et al. proposed three main objectives: establishing a good interpersonal relationship, exchanging information, and making treatment-related decisions [30]. Street et al. further emphasized the therapeutic value of communication, showing that validation of the patient's perspective and expressions of empathy may improve psychological well-being and support better healthcare outcomes [31].

In neurology, communication has additional complexity because many disorders may affect cognition, language, memory, executive function, emotional regulation, or the patient's ability to describe symptoms. Stern et al. emphasized that neurologists should focus on disease identification, shared decision-making, and care planning throughout the consultation process [32]. Anestis et al. identified several priorities for improving communication in neurological practice, including sufficient time for diagnosis, appropriate involvement of relatives or caregivers, realistic hope, and continued communication training for neurologists [33]. Ortega et al. highlighted the need to integrate professional interpreters and translators when caring for linguistically diverse neurological patients [34].

Because many neurological disorders are chronic, disabling, or progressive, the neurologist must provide not only medical information but also emotional support, while respecting the patient's autonomy, dignity, and individual preferences [35–39]. Communication in neurology therefore extends beyond diagnosis and treatment recommendations. It also includes empathy, ethical decision-making, disclosure of serious diagnoses, communication with cognitively impaired patients, caregiver involvement, and the construction of long-term therapeutic relationships [40–47].

This dimension is also relevant to Lifestyle Medicine. Patients with chronic neurological disorders often require sustained behavioral recommendations related to physical activity, nutrition, sleep, stress management, smoking cessation, and medication adherence. Clear, empathetic, and individualized communication can help transform these recommendations from abstract medical advice into realistic long-term actions that support neurological health and overall well-being.

DISCUSSION

Medical communication: between semiotics and pragmatics

Medical communication is a complex process through which health-related information is transmitted, received, interpreted, and transformed into clinical decisions. Its purpose is not only to explain disease or treatment, but also to support understanding, trust, and cooperation between physician and patient. In neurology, this process is particularly delicate, because cognitive, language, or emotional impairments may interfere with the patient’s ability to understand information, express concerns, or participate in medical decisions.

From a semiotic perspective, medical communication involves the interpretation of signs. Physicians interpret symptoms, behaviors, facial expressions, gestures, tone of voice, and verbal responses, while patients interpret the physician’s explanations, recommendations, and attitudes. Clear language is important, especially when explaining diagnoses, investigations, or treatment plans. However, precision alone is not sufficient. Empathy, emotional support, and sensitivity to the patient’s level of health literacy are also necessary for understanding and trust.

From a pragmatic perspective, communication must always be adapted to context. The same message may be received differently depending on the patient’s emotional state, cognitive abilities, sociocultural background, previous medical experiences, and expectations. For this reason, neurologists should adjust the amount and complexity of information, encourage questions, verify understanding, and allow enough time for the patient to respond.

The interaction between these perspectives is summarized in Table 1, which illustrates how verbal, nonverbal, and paraverbal communication contribute to clinical dialogue. These components do not function separately; they act together throughout the consultation and shape the quality of the therapeutic relationship.

TABLE 1. Semiotic and pragmatic perspective on medical communication

Medical communication			
Semiotic perspective		Components of communication	Pragmatic perspective
Communication as a system of signs			Communication as action in context
Language code	←	Verbal communication	→ The act of speech
Body code	←	Nonverbal communication	→ Relationship management
Voice code	←	Paraverbal communication	→ Communicative intention

In long-term neurological care, communication also has practical value for lifestyle-oriented recommendations. Patients are more likely to follow advice on physical activity, sleep, nutrition, stress management, smoking cessation, or medication adherence when explanations are clear, realistic, and adapted to their personal circumstances. In this sense, communication becomes part of the therapeutic process itself, not merely a vehicle for transmitting information.

The semiotic and pragmatic perspectives in verbal, nonverbal, and paraverbal communication

During outpatient neurological consultations, dialogue may be affected by cognitive impairment, aphasia, dementia, memory deficits, attention disorders, or other neurological conditions that limit comprehension and expression. Communication should therefore be adapted to the patient’s cognitive abilities, emotional state, and individual needs, while preserving a respectful and empathetic approach.

Effective communication requires both clinical reasoning and interpersonal sensitivity. The neurologist must obtain the information needed for diagnosis and treatment, but must also create a relationship in which the patient feels listened to, understood, and supported. This emotional dimension is especially important in chronic or progressive neurological disorders, where uncertainty, fear, and loss of autonomy may strongly influence the clinical encounter.

The way information is delivered should be individualized. Direct communication, using clear and explicit language, is useful when explaining investigations, diagnoses, or therapeutic recommendations. A more gradual and supportive approach may be preferable when discussing difficult news, uncertain prognosis, or long-term limitations. The choice of style should depend on the clinical situation, the patient’s personality, cultural background, health literacy, and preferences.

Although communication styles may vary across cultures, each patient remains an individual. For this reason, physicians should avoid relying only on general cultural assumptions and should instead observe how each patient responds. The main objective is for the patient to understand the information, feel respected, and remain actively involved in the consultation.

(1) Verbal communication remains the main way of exchanging clinical information. Language should be clear, concise, and adapted to the patient’s level of understanding. Medical jargon and ambiguous terms should

be avoided or carefully explained. Open-ended questions allow patients to describe symptoms, concerns, and expectations in their own words, supporting both diagnostic accuracy and patient-centered care. Written information may also be useful, especially when patients need more time to process recommendations or wish to review instructions after the consultation.

(2) Nonverbal communication also shapes the quality of the consultation. Facial expression, posture, gestures, eye contact, and interpersonal distance may influence trust, empathy, and the patient's feeling of safety. Attentive posture, appropriate eye contact, and supportive facial expressions usually facilitate dialogue, while dismissive or incongruent nonverbal behavior may create barriers. Observing the patient's nonverbal cues may also help the clinician recognize anxiety, uncertainty, discomfort, or emotional distress that is not directly expressed.

(3) Paraverbal communication refers to tone, volume, rhythm, pace, and pauses. These elements strongly influence how medical information is received. A calm and respectful voice, delivered at an appropriate pace, may reduce anxiety and improve understanding. By contrast, an excessively rapid, loud, or authoritarian style may discourage questions and limit patient participation. Pauses are also useful, as they give patients time to process information, formulate questions, and participate in shared decision-making.

Verbal, nonverbal, and paraverbal communication should therefore be understood as parts of the same clinical interaction. When used coherently, they help neurologists communicate more clearly, strengthen therapeutic relationships, and support patient engagement. These skills are also relevant for long-term lifestyle recommendations, where adherence depends not only on what the physician advises, but also on how realistic, understandable, and meaningful the advice becomes for the patient.

CONCLUSION

Effective doctor–patient communication represents a fundamental component of high-quality neurological care. Beyond facilitating information exchange, communication contributes to diagnostic accuracy, shared decision-making, treatment adherence, patient satisfaction, and the establishment of a strong therapeutic relationship.

This narrative review highlights three complementary perspectives that may enrich communica-

tion during outpatient neurological consultations. The diachronic perspective provides the historical foundations of communication theory; the semiotic perspective emphasizes the interpretation of signs, symbols, and meanings; and the pragmatic perspective focuses on the appropriate use of communication within specific clinical contexts. Together, these approaches offer a broader conceptual framework for understanding interactions between neurologists and their patients.

Successful communication in neurology requires the appropriate integration of verbal, nonverbal, and paraverbal communication while adapting the dialogue to each patient's cognitive status, emotional needs, health literacy, and sociocultural background. Such an individualized approach may strengthen patient engagement and facilitate collaborative clinical decision-making.

From the perspective of Lifestyle Medicine, effective communication extends beyond the consultation itself. It is an essential instrument for encouraging healthy behaviors, supporting long-term adherence to lifestyle recommendations, improving self-management of chronic neurological conditions, and fostering sustainable behavioral change.

Future research should evaluate communication strategies using empirical study designs and investigate their impact on patient satisfaction, treatment adherence, lifestyle modification, clinical outcomes, and quality of life among individuals with neurological disorders.

Conflict of interest:

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

Author's contributions:

The author confirms sole responsibility for the conception, drafting, revision, and final approval of the manuscript.

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